

ISSN 0975-4067

KIRANĀVALĪ

Journal of Sanskrit Research Foundation

The New Triyandrum Sanskrit Series
Vol. XIV, Book. III -IV

JULY - DECEMBER 2022

SRET

किरणावली
Sanskrit Research Foundation
Thiruvananthapuram

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Spell Checker for Sanskrit Sentences based on Morphological Analysis

Dr. Namrata Tapaswi¹

Abstract

Sanskrit (संस्कृत), sometimes referred to as the mother of all Indian languages, has a significant presence in Indian literature. The Sanskrit language is thought to be the source of all Indian languages. Sanskrit is a free ordering language (or syntax free language), which means that even if the sequence of the words changes, the meaning remains the same. The complexity of spell-checking documents in Sanskrit can be studied using morphological analysis, which is a basic component of language processing for Indian languages. We used morphological analysis to examine a huge number of words from various areas of speech. Based on this research, a spellchecker was created. The architecture of a spellchecker and a spell-checking algorithm constructed on morphological principles are proposed in this study.

Keywords

Morphology, Noun, Verb, Tagging, Syntax, Semantic, Part-of-speech.

1. Introduction

Words can be defined from grammatically, semantically, syntactically, lexically, socially, phonologically, morphologically, orthographically, and psycho-linguistically viewpoints (Gildea and Jurafsky,2002). Morphologically rich languages have a significant number of morphemes in a single word, with morpheme boundaries that are difficult to distinguish due to their fusion. Fixed-context systems are rarely adequate for statistical techniques since they are often free-word ordered. The text that spellcheckers input is a stream

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of orthographic words. Spell and grammar checkers have diverse points of view. The former relies heavily on vocabulary, but the later necessitates the use of grammar rules. Rules can also be used by spell checkers to reduce vocabulary size. Because of their morphological diversity, spell checkers for pan-Indian languages should use a rule-based approach. There are no dictionaries covering all conceivable inflections, derivations, and compounds obtainable from root words in Indian ancient language Sanskrit. The dictionary does not contain all commonly used Sanskrit words.

Each word contain:

- Three numbers (*vachan*, वचन): singular (*ekvachan*, एकवचन), dual (*dvivachan*, द्विवचन) and plural (*bahuvachan*, बहुवचन)
- Seven Vibhakti (*vibhakti*, विभक्ति): *prathama* प्रथमा, *dvitiya* द्वितीया, *thritiya* तृतीया, *chaturthi* चतुर्थी, *panchami* पञ्चमी , *shashthi* षष्ठी and *saptami* सप्तमी
- Three Gender (ling, लिङ्ग): *punling* पुलिङ्ग, *striling* स्त्रिलिङ्ग and *npunasakling* नपुंसकलिङ्ग

As a result, a noun might have up to 21 alternative forms (*shabdarupa* शब्दरूप), each with its own meaning. There could be over 100 adjectives or adverbs for a single word in Sanskrit. A verb, on the other hand, can take over 250 different forms. Morphologically rich languages have a significant number of morphemes in a particular word, with morpheme boundaries that are difficult to distinguish due to their fusion (Chinnakotla et al. 2008). Fixed-context systems are rarely adequate for statistical techniques since they are often free-word ordered.

Other advantages of a morphology-based spell checker include its capability to tackle the name-identity problem, which means it can engross new words that aren't in the dictionary. By categorizing new words into suitable paradigms, they can be digested. Furthermore, the method can be used to create grammatical checkers. The morphological rule base is one of the spellchecker approaches used in natural language processing. The rule-based tagger is those that use rules to determine which tags should be applied to acceptable terms (Kusumawardhan, 2013). The planning and application of a

rule-based spell checker for Sanskrit language are discussed in this paper. The spelling checker is constructed on morphological and orthographic criteria.

2. Language Structure

The Devanagari script is used to write Sanskrit. It uses one-to-one mapping to convert a word's phonemic form (phonemes and their sequence) to Devanagari symbols (Kulkarni and Ramakrishnam,2011). The Sanskrit spell checkers must take into account the symbols for three consonants (*vyanjan* व्यञ्जन: स्पर्श, अन्तः स्थ, ऊष्म), three vowels (*swar* स्वर : ह्रस्व स्वर , दीर्घ स्वर , सन्धि स्वर) , three person (*purush* पुरुष: प्रथम पुरुष , मध्यम पुरुष , उत्तम पुरुष), two *dhatu* (परस्मै पद , आत्मने पद) and fifteen matras. The existence of a specific vowel at a specific location in the phonemic representation of the word is indicated by *matras*. Instead of showing the existence of the phoneme “*schwa*,” a particular *matra* known as *halant* expresses its absence.

The rule (*schwa* -> ि) is implemented in the alphabet e (m) in the morphological conversion of word *nara* नर to word *narah* नरा . The vowel *schwa* is not present in the Unicode version of something like the word *nara* नर . Furthermore, in the transforming of word *gop* गोप to word *gopi* गोपी (गोप + ई = गोपी)), rule (*matra* ई -> *schwa* is applied on alphabet *p* प , but *schwa* does not appear in the unicode form of the word. The spellchecker must examine the word from an orthographic standpoint, using the above-mentioned orthographic rules. The penultimate vowel in a word is frequently written in its long form if the last vowel is *schwa*. In such circumstances, the root word's long penultimate vowel (ī or ū , I or U) is transformed to a short vowel (i or u) after morphological changes.

3. Literature Survey

Various morphological investigations have been conducted. a method for determining the semantic links, or semantic roles, that constituents of a sentence fulfil within a semantic frame (Gildea and Jurafsky,2002). Prefixes, Suffixes, and other affixation processes included. It also sheds some light on the (partially) word generation process in the Khasi language (Mishra et al.,2022). The perception of irregular and regular English verb forms in monolinguals and

bilinguals using a cross-modal priming approach investigated (Brown et al.,2007). Errors in morphology, syntax, and other areas could be found. By examining the errors, the hope is that the learners' mistakes may be remedied, preventing future faults in writing and allowing them to compose a good English narrative composition (Kusumawardhan, 2013). The objectives were to discover the processes of word production in new English words and to determine which of these processes was the most fruitful (s) identified (Ratih and Ismayoeng,2018). The lexical analyzer can be used in the Natural Language Processing domain of Machine Translation (by mapping the parse tree of Sanskrit language with other). It's difficult to grasp the true meaning of a term. Sentences are classified into four components by "*sandhi-wichched*": morphological lexical analysis, syntactic analysis, semantic analysis, and context analysis (Tapaswi and Jain, 2011). An intermediate parse with great tree structure computational features, and maybe another layer to create such tree structure more usable for information retrieval and user comprehension (Kulkarni and Ramakrishnam, 2011). The internal structure of the Noun Phrase (NP) in Urdu. It also provides a computational grammar based on the LFG formalism (Lexical Functional Grammar) (Ali et al., 2011). Investigated differences in Sanskrit linguistic treatment in the Sanskrit Heritage platform1 and the Paninian grammatical tradition (Goyal and Huet, 2013). for the Hindi language, a statistical POS tagger and chunker presented. Also created several models for the task that follow the principle of maximum entropy and can be used to tag unseen text (Dalal et al., 2010). Suitable feature engineering based on linguistic features, minimise the amount of data required by machine learning approaches used (Gune et al., 2010). Hindi to English and Marathi to English CLIR systems produced (Chinnakotla et al. 2008). Hindi as an example to discuss the construction of a spell-checker for Indian languages. Bangla is the second most widely spoken language in India (Choudhari, 2002). The entire design and execution of a Spell Checker for Kashmir presented (Lawaye and Purkayastha,2016).

We conduct a qualitative analysis of our findings by looking at the categorization of many high-impact papers. We recommend the

framework of the spell checker and the spell-checking algorithm based on morphological principles after consulting with leading experts and textbook authors in the field.

4. Morphological Rules

Noun, pronoun, verb, adverb, adjective, postposition, conjunction, and interjection are all subjected to morphological analysis (Brown et al., 2007). In Sanskrit, rules of substitution are useful for capturing various forms of morphological activity (Tapaswi and Jain, 2011), such as those recorded in the examples below.

1. As in the transformation of *narah* नरः to word *narah* नराः as explained above, changes to a word's phonemic shape at the conclusion of the word taking into account the latent *schwa*.
2. Changes in the phonemic shape of a word that occur not only at the conclusion of the word but also in the midst, as in transformation of *jagat* *ishah* जगत् ईशः to *jagadishah* जगदीशः
3. All vowels in the phonemic shape of the word are changed, such as in conversions of *naro ayam* नरो अयम् to *naroyam* नरोऽयम्.
4. Other instances include the deletion of the last or penultimate consonant of the word, as well as the addition of a consonant and vowel combination at the end.

The replacement rules are broad enough to encompass all possible consonant and vowel additions and deletions. Replacement rules take into account *latent schwa* and *null* components if needed. Postpositions are used to affix oblique forms of nominal and verbal elements in Sanskrit language. As a result, for morphological study of these categories, postposition morphology is critical. The majority of the rules can be written as transformation tables. Additional syntactic rules are used to capture the order of suffixes. Over 1,000 base words have already been gathered and categorised according to their function. In order to generate inflectional morphological rules for each word categories, analysis was undertaken. Tenses, aspects, moods, and genders, as well as the numbers, persons, and attachments of postpositions, were all taken into account.

4.1 Morphology of Postposition

Postpositional paradigms are developed based on their language behaviours. Case markers (*vibhakti pratyay*) and a group of postpositions known as *shabdayogi avyay* are among them. The words are connected to nouns and pronouns in both singular and plural forms. Some *shabdayogi avyays* have distinct personalities. When postpositions follow syllable *ah* अः, which is a case marker, for example, they must be written separately. The *vibhakti pratyay a* अः, *au* औ, and *āh* आः (v) can be suffixed to several *shabdayogi avyays*. Some *shabdayogi avyays* can be made up of other *shabdayogi avyays*. Before some *shabdayogi avyays*, the postpositions *he* हे and *au* औ can be used, but not without *vibhakti pratyays*. Some *shabdayogi avyays* could be used with various oblique verb forms. In the above classification, the spellchecker currently only analyzes the first degree of postpositions.

4.2 Morphology of Nouns

The alterations caused by the attachment of post positions differ in the single and plural forms of noun). The *Sāmānya roop* (oblique form) of a word to which such attachment is made is called that noun's modified form. For example, when the word *narah* नरः is morphologically converted into the word *narau* नरौ, the *samanya roop* of *narah* नरः is *narah* नराः .

4.3 Morphology of Pronouns

All *shabdayogi avyays* are tied to a distinct single indirect form of a pronoun. Because pronouns have such erratic behaviour hence compiled a list of conceivable (over 200) inflections for pronouns.

4.4 Morphology of Verbs

Ākhyāta Theory is the foundation of verb morphological analysis. It divides verb structures under verb roots and ending suffixes known as Ākhyātas in a methodical manner. Ākhyāta is a symbolic representation of knowledge about a person's mood and personality. They're called tākhyāta, vākhyāta, and lākhyāta after their phonemic shapes. A simple verb root can create over 100 different forms. There are around 40 irregular verbs in addition to regular verbs (Gune et al., 2010).

4.5 Morphology of Adjectives

Inflectional and non-inflectional adjectives are divided into two types. Gender, number, and attaching of postpositions towards the noun changed by the adjective cause inflections. Adjectives are formed whenever genitive case markers or other Shabdayogi avyays are connected to nouns. Noun morphology automatically covers these forms.

4.6 Morphology of Adverbs, Conjunctions and Interjections

This is a significant group of parts of speech for which the rule-based approach has proven effective. One of the ways for adverb construction is to attach postpositions to nouns, verbs, and pronouns. There are other adverbs that are not inflectional. At the morphological level of postpositions, nouns, verbs, and pronouns, the set of derived adverbs is generally covered. It is compiled from a number of all lexicalized adverbs. Because conjunctions and interjections are non-inflectional, they are also treated as a list. Conjunctions are formed whenever some postpositions are linked to demonstrative pronouns. These are dealt with at the level of pronoun and postposition rules.

5. Implementation

A word's validity is checked using an algorithm.

- 1) Continue to step 2 if the word w is still not found in the dictionary; else, take the word and stop.
- 2) From right to left, scan the word w for a valid suffix string " s_2 " that appears in at least one criterion of the type ($s_1 \rightarrow s_2$). It's worth noting that s_1 and s_2 may be longer than 1, and that s_1 could be a substring in s_2 . If no such rule can be discovered, discard the word as incorrect and move on to step 3, else go to step 3.
- 3) Apply a conversion ($s_2 \rightarrow s_1$) to the back end of the word to get the trimmed word w_1 from w . Accept w_1 as a legitimate word and proceed to step 4 if the converted word w_1 is available in vocabulary and the rule ($s_1 \rightarrow s_2$) is acceptable again for word class of w_1 .
- 4) Return to step 2 to look for another rule that applies. If a word is deemed to be invalid, options are given based on left-to-right matching, inflectional rules, and string dis-

tance. In addition to morphological analysis, a spell-checker analyses spelling norms, as explained in Section 2. Java is used to implement the spellchecker. The papers are converted to Unicode for display.

6. The Spellchecker's Structure Layout

Figure1: Spellchecker's Structure Layout

Figure1 shows the Spellchecker's Structure Layout. The front end of the system enables spell checking for Sanskrit texts by utilizing the services delivered by the spell checker's interface (SCI). To process documents in various formats, a font converter is available. For the display unit, Unicode is utilized. Text processing, storage format conversion, marking of invalid words, and management of user actions on them are all supported on the front end. A user can ignore, replace, or add a highlighted term to their vocabulary. Alternatives are offered based on morphological rules and a string distance. The Morphology Analyzer (MA) consults the SCI, which consults particular part of speech analyzers covering nouns, adjectives, verbs, and other categories. As indicated in Figure 1, the separate parts of speech analyzers are using their own rule bases. In addition, a user-level wordlist can be added.

7. Evaluation

A manual examination of 1500 words from a corpus that were

pronounced genuine by the spellchecker revealed that 15 of them were incorrect. This meant that the veracity of the data was 99 percent accurate. The causes of the errors were identified back to a lack of rule implementation and unique circumstances.

Additionally, a manual examination of terms labelled invalid revealed that a significant number of them were incorrectly classified as invalid. The main causes were found to be inadequate vocabulary and numerous ordered suffixes, both of which were not handled in the present version. The vocabulary is now limited to around 13,000 terms. The accuracy will improve if the vocabulary is improved.

Misspelled root words, misspelt or improper suffixes, and the incorrect order of attachment of several suffixes are all examples of errors that might arise. Recommendations for erroneous words are based on the root, stem forming suffix, and case marker or postposition, which are the three parts of the word. To find all potential proper formulations, depth first technique is applied. A proposed phrase may differ by one vowel and one consonant at most. Ultimately, all of the recommendations are ordered by string distance. If somehow the input word is misspelt by a vowel and/or a consonant, this strategy was shown to get the predicted term in the first three suggestions in the majority of the situations that were evaluated.

8. Conclusion

For several parts of speech categories, morphological analysis was performed on over 800 Sanskrit word forms. The number of potential inflections of a single word is enormous, as is typical of Indian languages. Some of the difficulties in developing a spellchecker capable of dealing with such a complicated linguistic issue were explored (Choudhari, 2002). A first-level suffix spellchecker design and implementation based on morphological analysis and orthography norms was given. Preliminary tests revealed that the method was very accurate in determining the validity of words. More improvements to derivational morphology will aid in the expansion of the vocabulary. Improvements to expressing rules for ordering multiple suffixes throughout all parts of speech categories

are necessary, in addition to word lists and rules. More extensive orthographic rules need to be added.

Further syntactic and semantic analysis can be added to a morphology-based spellchecker. The Centre for Indian Languages is now using morphology-based analysis in a few applications, in addition to spell checking. The cornerstone for POS-tagging is the morphological study of a word. Similarly, in Sanskrit Wordnet, it is employed in stemming to find root words.

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KIRANĀVALĪ
Journal of Sanskrit Research Foundation
The New Trivandrum Sanskrit Series Vol. XIV.
Book III-IV
JULY – DECEMBER 2022

ISSN 0975-4067

Printed and published by: Dr.C.S.Sasikumar, Secretary, Sanskrit Research Foundation, Thiruvananthapuram, for Sanskrit Research Foundation, Thiruvananthapuram-36
Sanskritresearchfoundation@gmail.com